

STAGES OF THE ORIENTATION OF FOREIGN CASTINGS TO TOURISM.

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Annotation: this article is aimed at creating for itself all the conditions necessary for the effective functioning of investors in the tourism sector. Uzbekistan's location on a geographically favorable land, the development of the transport network, the abundance of Natural Resources, high development of production and social infrastructure, the presence of personnel in tourism organizations and other factors have given investors the opportunity to look at the future with confidence.

Keywords: investment flows, internal flows, free economic territory.

In order to improve the territorial conditions and solve problems in the direction of the country's tourism flows, with the participation of specialists of enterprises with foreign castings, specialist representatives of regional municipalities, heads of large companies and enterprises with the possibility of castings and mature scientists of the Republic in the field of tourism, an open dialogue should be organized between the general public and On this basis, it is necessary to develop and ensure the viability of a unified policy of scientific and economic based castings among specialists, scientists and practitioners, as well as a mechanism for working in practice on the adopted laws and decisions, while attracting broad public opinion to the issue.

There are obstacles and shortcomings in this regard. A clear example of this is the fact that foreign direct flows into the tourism sectors, which are the main

indicators that determine the state of the flow of flows into the country, do not increase the flow to tourism sectors sufficiently.

In this regard, the following measures should be carried out in order to develop the effectiveness of foreign castings in the tourism sectors and directly increase the flow of foreign castings to the tourism market:

It would be advisable to consider this problem only in terms of increasing the consumption capacity of residents and enterprises, increasing the level of healthy demand for manufactured goods and services, without looking for a solution, which depends on foreign castings themselves. The weak conduct of marketing research as one of the factors affecting the flow of foreign castings in tourism (which applies not only to foreign, but also to multilateral domestic castings), as a result of which many manufactured products remain residual in warehouses. To solve this issue, alternative and independent non-state information agents should be established.

The provision of unbiased and reliable information about the financial indicators of tourism organizations and financial indicators has not been well established.

The current task, which concerns the collective grounds for attracting foreign castings to tourism, is the formation of long — term stable positions of the government on foreign castings and its delivery to potential foreign investors.

Step-by-step improvement of the economic structure, which fully meets the internal needs of our country, expansion of the scope of foreign economic activity based on rational and efficient use of our natural and economic resources is one of the main guarantees of ensuring stable growth and balanced macroeconomic indicators of our economy at a high pace.

The involvement of foreign foreign castings in tourism through the establishment of foreign enterprises is expanding today. Enterprises with the participation of foreign castings in Uzbekistan can be organized in different spheres of the economy. Large foreign companies and enterprises can separate a part of their

property and open various enterprises. The requirements for joint ventures are also set for such enterprises.

More than two or three countries or enterprises can form international organizations with their capital concentrated.

And the lease agreement is the long - term lease of equipment, equipment and technologies with the participation of tourism organizations of foreign castings. Tenders, on the other hand, are the involvement of investors on a competitive basis to finance casting projects. A free Economic Area is an area in which foreign foreign castings freely enter and a number of privileges are established in a given area.

Today, preferential financial conditions have been created for them on the basis of the law in order to attract foreign castings to tourism in a wider range, to interest foreign investors in spending their funds for the tourism of the country, including ¹:

- * guarantees for the preservation of the capital of foreign investors;
- * guarantees to cover losses incurred;
- * established benefits regarding them in the taxation system;
- * freedom to take profits and profits abroad;
- * possibility of transfer and withdrawal of profits received in national sums and foreign currencies;
- * availability of Customs privileges;
- the creation of a system of insurance protection of property of foreign investors and their own risks.

The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on the territories of the free economy" defines the free economic territory as follows: "Free Economic territories are a specially designated territory with clearly defined administrative boundaries and a special legal order shot to death in order to attract country and foreign capital, promising technology and management experience for the rapid socio – economic

¹ Shodmonov Sh.Sh., Gafurov U.V. The globalization process and the causes of the financial crisis.. // February 27, 2009

development of the region." In the process of establishing free economic territories, the state should be the chief reformer as a supporter, promoter and controller. The participation of the state as the chief initiator is clearly manifested in the experience of foreign investments.

As a result, national and, mainly, foreign investors began to enter the territories foreign deposits, which, in turn, served as the basis for the development of the country's economy.

In conclusion, it is necessary to support the credit capacity of the country, the prestige of Uzbekistan as a first-class lending country. It is necessary to avoid illegal interference by state and control agencies in the activities of foreign investments with the participation of tourism organizations. Taking into account precisely the natural and economic potential of the regions, it is necessary for each region to determine the prevailing directions for attracting foreign investments to tourism.

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